

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Hexa-aquo-chromium(III) with Bismuth(v) in HClO₄-HF Mixture

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Kinetics of the oxidation of hexaaquochromium(III) with bismuth(v) in HClO₄-HF mixture follow the rate law,

$$-\frac{1}{3} \frac{d[\text{BiV}]}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d[\text{CrVI}]}{dt} = \left\{ k_1 + \frac{k_2 k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \right\} [\text{BiV}]_T [\text{CrIII}]_T$$

The energy of activation for k_1 and k_2 paths were calculated to be (39 ± 4) and (11 ± 1) kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The entropy of activation for these paths were -136 ± 12 and -150 ± 12 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ at 35°. A probable reaction model based on outer-sphere bridged activated complex has been suggested.

CHROMIUM(III) is an important species of d^3 -configuration, which is kinetically inert to substitution. The chemistry of bismuth(v) has useful synthetic and analytical applications¹. Nevertheless, the solution chemistry of bismuth(v) has not yet been explored fully due to its low solubility and high oxidising strength in common solvents. However, the digestion of sodium bismuthate in a mixture of HClO₄-HF gives a transparent solution appreciably stable at ambient temperature². The title reaction was undertaken to elucidate the mode of electron transfer from Cr^{III} to Bi^V.

Experimental

Sodium bismuthate (Reidel, A.R.) was used as a source of bismuth(v). The preparation and standardisation of the bismuth(v) solution in HClO₄-HF mixture were given elsewhere³. Freshly prepared bismuth(v) solutions were always used.

Chromium(III) solutions were prepared by dissolving chromium(III) hydroxide (free of sulphate ions) in dilute HClO₄. Chromium(III) hydroxide was precipitated by the addition of sodium hydroxide to an aqueous solution of chromium(III) sulphate. These solutions were left for a few days before standardising spectrophotometrically⁴. All other chemicals were either of AnalaR or guaranteed reagent grade. Double-distilled water was used, second distillation being from alkaline permanganate solution.

Kinetics of the reaction were carried out in a water-bath thermostated at $35.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$ unless stated otherwise. Reaction was initiated by the addition of known volume of chromium(III) solution to the temperature-equilibrated reaction mixture containing bismuth(v) and other reaction ingredients. An aliquot (5 or 10 cm³) of the reaction mixture was withdrawn at different intervals of time and chromium(vi) was analysed spectrophotometrically.

A few reactions were also conducted in flasks painted black from the outside. However, rate is not affected by straylight.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry : The stoichiometry of the reaction with an excess concentration of chromium(III) over that of bismuth(v) was found (Table 1) to correspond to the reaction as represented by equation (1),

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRIC RESULTS FOR REACTION OF BISMUTH(V) WITH CHROMIUM(III) IN HClO₄-HF MIXTURES
[HClO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [HF]=1.5 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=35°

[BiV] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[CrIII] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[CrVI] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³ Found/(Calcd.)
1.02	2.0	0.59 (0.68)
1.02	3.0	0.60 (0.68)
1.12	2.0	0.66 (0.74)
1.12	4.0	0.69 (0.74)
1.30	3.0	0.82 (0.86)
1.30	4.0	0.84 (0.86)
1.70	3.0	1.01 (1.13)
1.70	4.0	1.05 (1.13)

The difference in observed and calculated Cr^{VI} concentrations is slightly large in lower concentrations of the reactants, that in all probability can be ascribed to two main reasons. Firstly, since the reactions at lower concentrations of the reactants require longer time for completion, the decomposition of bismuth(v) to the extent of 10% at maximum might take place. Secondly, chromium(III) solutions may contain 3-4% dimeric or polymeric species which usually are not reactive towards oxidants.

Bismuth(v) and chromium(III) dependence : The concentrations of bismuth(v) and chromium(III) were varied in the ranges $(1.0-5.0) \times 10^{-3}$ and

(2.0–25.0) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ respectively, at fixed concentrations of [HClO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³ and [HF]=1.5 mol dm⁻³. Initial rates were computed by plane mirror method⁵. The plot of initial rates (i.r.) against the respective concentrations of Bi^V and Cr^{III} yielded straight lines passing through the origin indicating order with respect to each reactant to be one. The second order rate constants (*k'*) calculated from initial rates at 35° are collected in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR REACTION OF BISMUTH(V) AND CHROMIUM(III)

[HClO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [HF]=1.5 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=35°

[Bi ^V] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[Cr ^{III}] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	(i.r.) × 10 ⁶ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	<i>k</i> × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
1.00	6.0	2.6	14.3
1.50	6.0	4.0	14.6
2.20	6.0	5.6	14.0
2.50	6.0	6.3	14.0
3.00	6.0	7.6	14.0
3.60	6.0	9.6	14.0
4.60	6.0	11.0	14.3
5.60	6.0	14.6	14.3
2.20	2.0	1.8	13.3
2.20	4.0	3.1	13.0
2.20	6.0	5.4	13.0
2.20	8.0	6.8	13.0
2.20	10.0	8.9	13.3
2.20	12.0	10.8	13.3
2.20	14.0	12.0	13.0
2.20	16.0	14.2	13.0
2.20	18.0	16.1	13.0
2.20	20.0	18.4	13.6
2.20	22.0	22.2	13.0
2.20	25.0	22.6	13.0

Hydrogen ion dependence: Hydrogen ion concentration was varied by changing the concentration of HClO₄ at constant concentrations of the reactants and also fixed ionic strength (*I*=2.0 mol dm⁻³, adjusted with lithium perchlorate). The rate of the reaction decreases with increasing concentration of hydrogen ion as represented by an experimental rate law (2),

$$\frac{d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = k'[\text{Bi}^{\text{V}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} \quad (2)$$

where second order rate constant $k' = A + (B/[\text{H}^+])$; *A* and *B* are hydrogen ion independent and dependent constants. [Bi^V]_T and [Cr^{III}]_T are the gross analytical concentrations of all fluoro species of bismuth(v) and chromium(III) respectively.

Since hydrogen fluoride has a pK ~ 3 in aqueous solution, hence the contribution of hydrogen ion from HF in HClO₄ (1.0 mol dm⁻³) was not considered to account for the total hydrogen ion concentration in the solution.

Effect of HF and fluoride ions: The rate of reaction remains unchanged in HF concentration range 0.75–2.0 mol dm⁻³. The [HF]=0.5 mol dm⁻³ was not employed in view of the known⁸ slow deterioration of bismuth(v) solution. Similarly, the rate of reaction is not affected by the sodium fluoride

concentration in the range (0.1–0.5) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³. These effects are supportive of the fact that the ultimate fluoro species of bismuth(v) (BiF₆⁻) is formed in 1.5 mol dm⁻³ HF and 1.0 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ concentrations.

Bismuth(III) and chromium(VI) dependence: Bismuth(III), a reaction product, has no effect on the rate of the reaction in the concentration range (1.0–8.0) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³. Similarly, the rate of the reaction remains unaffected by Cr^{VI}. Thus the probability of any fast pre-equilibrium involving either Bi^{III} or Cr^{VI} is eliminated.

Since the rate of the reaction is not affected by [HF] and [NaF] hence it is quite likely that either ultimate complex BiF₆⁻ saturated with fluoride ions is formed or all the fluoro species of bismuth(v) are contributing equally to the overall rate of the reaction.

The extinction coefficients of chromium(III) solutions calculated at 408 and 574 nm are within the reported limits^{6,7} for Cr(H₂O)₆³⁺. Thus chromium(III) predominantly exists in the form of hexaaquochromium(III) in HF solutions.

The inverse hydrogen ion dependence may be accounted for assuming deprotonation of one coordinated water molecule in hexaaquochromium(III),

Rate law (4) derived from this mechanism is similar to the experimental rate law (2) provided $K_1 \ll [\text{H}^+]$,

$$-\frac{1}{3} \frac{d[\text{Bi}^{\text{V}}]}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = \left\{ k_1 + \frac{k_2 K_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \right\} [\text{Bi}^{\text{V}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } k' = k_1 + \frac{k_2 K_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (5)$$

where *k'*, the observed second order rate constant, has been calculated to be (13.6 ± 1.0) × 10⁻³ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 35°. A plot of *k'* against [H⁺]⁻¹ (Fig.1) yields a straight line with non-zero intercept. The *k*₁ values calculated from the intercept were found to be 5.0 × 10⁻², 8.9 × 10⁻² and 12.8 × 10⁻² dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 25, 35 and 45° respectively. However, the values of *k*₂ to be 7.5 × 10², 8.8 × 10² and 9.7 × 10² dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ were derived from the composite values of *k*₂*K*₁ employing the reported⁸ values of *K*₁, viz. 3.98 × 10⁻⁵, 6.6 × 10⁻⁵ and 9.8 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ at 25, 35 and 45° respectively. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated in a conventional manner.

The energy of activation for *k*₁ and *k*₂ paths were calculated to be (39 ± 4) and (11 ± 1) kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The entropy of activation calculated for these paths are -136 ± 12 and -150 ± 12 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ at 35° respectively. The low *E*_a but strongly

Fig. 1. $[BiV]=2.22 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[CrIII]=6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[HF]=1.5 M$, $I=2.0 M$, at temp.: (□) 25, (○) 35 and (△) 45°.

negative ΔS^\ddagger values may be explained if the following hydrogen-bonded intermediate is assumed. This causes a facile electron transfer from chromium(III) to bismuth(v).

Inverse hydrogen ion dependence can also be explained invoking the hydrolytic equilibrium step (5),

However, this proposal was abandoned in view of two observations. Firstly, such an inverse acid dependence has not been observed in other reactions of bismuth(v). It is, therefore, difficult to discriminate between this reaction and other reactions. Secondly, high concentration of HF employed in the reaction did not support equilibrium step (5) in absence of any effect of HF and fluoride ions on the rate of the reaction.

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